

The Lunar Electromagnetic Monitor in X-rays: conception, status and future perspectives

F. Ceraudo^{1,2,*}, M. Antonelli³, G. Bertuccio⁴, R. Campana⁵, M. Centis Vignali⁶, G. Della Casa^{1,2}, E. Del Monte^{1,2}, E. Demenev⁶, G. Dilillo^{7,8}, Y. Evangelista^{1,2}, M. Feroci^{1,2}, F. Ficorella⁶, M. Fiorini⁹, A. Gemelli¹⁰, E. Giancarli^{1,2,11}, J. Giani¹⁰, M. Grassi¹⁰, G. Lombardi^{1,2}, P. Malcovati¹⁰, F. Mele^{4,1}, A. Nuti^{1,2}, G. Pepponi⁶, T. Pisanu¹², A. Rachevski³, M. Rapisarda¹, I. Rashevskaya¹³, A. Samusenko⁵, A. Sharma⁵, M. Tambussi¹⁰, G. Zampa³, N. Zampa³, Y. Zhu⁴, N. Zorzi⁶, F. Esposito¹⁴, U. Cortesi¹⁵, I. Donnarumma⁸, F. D'Amico¹⁶, A. Turchi⁸, M. Gai¹⁴, A. Argan¹⁶ on behalf of the EMM team

*Corresponding author, francesco.ceraudo@inaf.it, ¹INAF – IAPS, Via del Fosso del Cavaliere 100, 00133, Roma (Italy), ²INFN – Sezione di Roma Tor Vergata, via della Ricerca Scientifica 1, 00133, Roma (Italy), ³INFN – Sezione di Trieste, Padriciano 99, 34149 Trieste (Italy), ⁴Politecnico di Milano – Dipartimento di Elettronica, Informazione e Bioingegneria, Via Ponzio 34/5, 20133 Milano (Italy), ⁵INAF – OAS, Via Gobetti 93/3, 40129 Bologna (Italy), ⁶Fondazione Bruno Kessler, Via Sommarive 18, 38123 Povo (Italy), ⁷INAF – OAR, Via Frascati 33, Rome 00078, Italy, ⁸Agenzia Spaziale Italiana, Via del Politecnico snc, 00133, Roma (Italy), ⁹INAF – IASF Milano, Via Alfonso Corti 12, 20133, Milano (Italy), ¹⁰Università di Pavia – Dipartimento di Ingegneria Industriale e dell'Informazione, Via Adolfo Ferrata 5, 27100 Pavia (Italy), ¹¹Sapienza Università di Roma – Dipartimento di Fisica, Piazzale A. Moro 5, 00185 Roma (Italy), ¹²INAF – Osservatorio Astronomico di Cagliari, Via della Scienza 5 - 09047 Selargius (Italy), ¹³TIFPA – INFN, Via Sommarive 14, 38123, Povo (Italy), ¹⁴INAF – Osservatorio Astronomico di Capodimonte, Salita Moiriello 16, 80131 Napoli (Italy), ¹⁵CNR – Istituto Di Fisica Applicata “Nello Carrara”, Via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino (Italy), ¹⁶INAF – Sede Centrale, Viale del Parco Mellini 84, 00136 Roma (Italy).

Introduction: The X-ray band uniquely ensures the sensitivity and location accuracy allowing to bridge the gap between the capabilities of current and next-generation gravitational wave and neutrino detectors, and those of optical telescopes in the search for the electromagnetic counterparts of exotic phenomena in the new age of Multi-Messenger Astrophysics [1]. Moreover, continuous monitoring of known sources, usually themselves subject to transient activity, can shed important light on the physics acting in the most extreme environments in the Universe. In this context, having continuous access to the whole sky is paramount. The Moon, thanks to its rotation and stable environment, potentially offers accessibility to the whole sky, as well as instrument serviceability, in the context of future permanent human infrastructures.

The instrument: The Lunar Electromagnetic Monitor in X-rays (LEM-X) is an all-sky observatory proposed for deployment on the surface of the Moon [2]. The instrument is composed of five pairs of coded-aperture cameras, each capable of imaging a large field of view (~ 1 sr at 25% effective area) in the X-ray band (2 - 50 keV) with a point source location accuracy of ~ 1 arcmin, and an on-axis sensitivity < 1 Crab in 1 s and < 5 mCrab in 50 ks. The camera detectors are also able to perform spectral-timing studies, with a spectral resolution < 350 eV at 6 keV and a timing resolution < 10 μ s. The five camera pairs are arranged in a dome-shaped structure to ensure full continuous coverage of the accessible sky.

Current activities: We have designed the engineering models of four Detector Assemblies (DAs) of a single LEM-X camera. Each DA is based on a large-area linear Silicon Drift Detector, read out by two rows of 11 Application Specific Integrated Circuits named NOVA [4,5], all mounted on a ceramic front-end board. The engineering models of the DAs

have been integrated, and the spectral and imaging capabilities of each device have been assessed in the laboratory through illumination via radio-isotopes and mapping via a micrometric X-ray beam.

In parallel, the design of the whole camera system, including the mask, the mechanical structure and the on-board electronics, is being carried out, in order to ensure the demanding scientific and operational requirements of the instrument are met.

Contribution: In this contribution, we will present the status of the LEM-X project, with particular focus on the results of the performance characterisation of the engineering models of the DAs. Future perspectives on the development of the instrument hardware and on the mission as a whole will be provided as well.

Acknowledgements: The activities related to the LEM-X Detector Assemblies have been carried out in the framework of the “Earth Moon Mars” (EMM) program, funded by the Italian Ministry of University and Research, within the context of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, under the leadership of the National Institute of Astrophysics (INAF) and in collaboration with the Italian Space Agency (ASI) and the National Research Council (CNR).

References:

- [1] Meszaros P. et al. (2019) *Nature Reviews Physics*, 1, 585–599
- [2] Del Monte E. et al. (2024) *SPIE Proceedings*, 13093, id. 130931U
- [3] Ceraudo F. et al. (2024) *SPIE Proceedings*, 13093, id. 130937N
- [4] Mele F. et al. (2025) *Proceedings of SIE 2024, Lecture Notes in Electrical Engineering*, 1263, Springer, Cham
- [5] Ceraudo F. et al., (2025) *IEEE NSS/MIC/RTSD*, doi: 10.1109/NSS/MIC/RTSD57106.2025.11286472.